

Synthesis, spectral characterization, thermal and antimicrobial studies of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) complexes with 1,2,4-triazole Schiff bases

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Abstract : A series of metal complexes of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} of type [Ln(L)Cl(H₂O)₂] have been synthesized with some biologically active ligands (LH₂). These ligands were prepared by the reactions of 3-[2-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)ethyl]-5-hydrazinyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-amine with aryl aldehyde/ketone. The structures of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, electrical conductance, magnetic moment, IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR and UV-Vis spectra. Thermal studies of the complexes are also reported. The Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been screened for antibacterial (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) and antifungal activities (*Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus*). The screening results have been correlated with the structural features of the compounds.

Keywords : Triazoles, lanthanide complexes, spectroscopic properties, thermal analysis, antimicrobial activities.

Introduction

The chemistry of metal complexes with heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen, sulfur, and/or oxygen as ligand atoms has attracted increasing attention. It is well known that the heterocyclic compounds exhibit bactericidal, fungicidal, herbicidal, and insecticidal activities in addition to their application as potential drugs. Such heterocyclic ligands, when complexed with metal ions, exhibit enhanced microbiological activities^{1,2}. The role of microelements in biochemical processes is well documented^{3,4}. However, the mechanisms by which ligands operate are not common to all bioactive molecules. These molecules are expected to possess a certain ability to form complexes with particular metals. The heterofunctional biomolecules form complexes with particular metals and their salts, bringing considerable changes in the physicochemical properties of the latter⁵. The coordination behavior of ligands bearing heterocycles, especially with transition-metal ions, has been studied extensively⁶⁻⁸. Major biological interest in the complexes of these ligands stems from their suitability in designing metal-containing model systems, which mimic biologically active systems. The presence of donor atoms (N, S, O) at various positions in these molecules enable them to behave as multidentate ligands and thus form chelates of diverse

structural types with a wide range of metal ions. The interaction of metal ions with biomolecules and the function of metal ions in physiological systems are very complex, and the precise mechanism of these interactions is almost unknown. In the synthetic systems, ligand design based on selective complexation with metal ions is limited to ideas, such as size-matched selectivity, drop in stability due to increased size of chelate and steric strain. However, the ligand activity is a combination of steric, electronic, and pharmacokinetic factors, and it could be understood in the light of chelation theory⁵. In this context, various heterocycles, especially azoles, occupy an important place owing to their versatile bioactivities due to the presence of multifunctional groups. Despite their biological significance and potential applications, lanthanide complexes of these ligands have not received special attention they rightly deserve. This is because complexation of lanthanide(III) ions differs from that of *d*-block elements. The development of tailored receptors for Ln^{III} remains a challenge to synthetic chemists, since lanthanide ions do not display pronounced stereochemical preferences for particular bonding modes⁹. Furthermore, lanthanide ions, in view of their electronic configuration and size, are often used as spectroscopic probe as surrogates for Ca²⁺ ion in studies of biological sys-

tems as well as promoters in dyeing industry and diagnostic agents in clinical medicine^{10,11}. The present investigation deals with the synthesis, characterization, thermal and antimicrobial studies of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 5-[2-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)ethyl]-4-amino-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol.

Experimental

The reagents and solvents were analytical grade, neodymium(III) chloride and samarium(III) chloride were purchased from Aldrich. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of 3-[2-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)ethyl]-5-hydrazinyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-amine with appropriate aldehyde/ketone as reported in the literature¹²⁻¹⁶ (Scheme 1).

Preparation of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes :

To a solution of appropriate ligand (1 mmol) in ethanol (20 cm³), the appropriate MCl₃ (M = Nd, Sm) (1 mmol) in ethanol (10 cm³) was added and the pH of the

reaction mixture was adjusted to *ca.* 5.5 by sodium hydroxide solution. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 12–18 h. The product formed was filtered, washed with water followed by ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yield : 59–75%.

The detail of the reactions along with the analytical data of the products are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements :

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method and neodymium or samarium was determined gravimetrically as neodymium oxide or samarium oxide. Melting points were determined on a Buchi 530 apparatus in open capillary tubes. IR spectra were recorded on a Matson 1000 model FTIR spectrophotometer as KBr disks. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol AL300 spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to an internal standard of Me₄Si. A Hitachi Japan model U-2000 spectrophoto-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Synthetic and analytical data for Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes

Sl. No.	Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Ln
1.	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClNd	68	182	45.98 (45.96)	3.71 (3.68)	14.44 (14.43)	21.24 (21.25)
2.	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	59	185	45.57 (45.55)	3.68 (3.65)	14.31 (14.30)	21.94 (21.95)
3.	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClNd	71	175	47.55 (47.54)	4.13 (4.10)	13.86 (13.86)	20.39 (20.40)
4.	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	65	180	47.14 (47.13)	4.10 (4.06)	13.74 (13.74)	21.08 (21.09)
5.	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClNd	75	189	52.40 (52.39)	3.75 (3.72)	12.58 (12.58)	18.51 (18.52)
6.	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	62	195	51.99 (51.98)	3.72 (3.69)	12.48 (12.48)	19.14 (19.15)

tometer was used to record the electronic spectra. Molar conductance of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO was recorded on a Hanna EC 215 conductivity meter by using 0.01 M KCl water solution as calibrant.

Antimicrobial studies :

The ligand and all newly prepared complexes were screened for their activity against three bacterial organisms *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96, *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 121, *Escherichia coli* MTCC 1652, and two fungi, *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus*, by agar well diffusion technique^{17,18}. All the bacterial cultures were procured from Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC), IMTECH, Chandigarh.

Inoculums of bacteria were prepared in nutrient broth and fungi in potato dextrose agar slant. The molten Muller Hinton medium was poured into a sterile petridish (9 cm in diameter) to get a depth of 4 mm. The medium was left to solidify. Thereafter, it was seeded with respective test organisms. About 8 mg of each sample to be tested was dissolved in 1 ml of DMSO and 5 mm discs of Whatmann filter paper no. 42 were cut and sterilized. The filter paper discs were immersed in a solution of sample. After soaking, the disc was removed and left in a sterile petridish to permit the solvent to evaporate. After about 10 min the paper discs were transferred to seeded agar plate. About 5 discs were kept on the seeded agar plates. Finally the dishes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h (for bacteria) and at 30 °C for 72 h (for fungi), where clear or inhibition

zones were detected around each disc.

A disc soaked in DMSO alone was used as a control under the same conditions and there was no observed inhibition zone for DMSO. Each distinct inhibition zone was measured as diameter in mm, both antibacterial and antifungal activity can be calculated as a mean of three replicates.

Results and discussion

All Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes are coloured, stable in room temperature, non hygroscopic, insoluble in water and many common organic solvents. All the complexes are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but these complexes are soluble to a larger extent in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance values are in the range of 8–12 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, indicating their non-electrolytic behaviour in solution.

Magnetic behaviour :

The magnetic moment values of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) complexes are found to be in the range 3.40–3.48 μ_B and 1.52–1.56 μ_B, respectively. The observed magnetic moment values suggest that the Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} are paramagnetic. As the magnetic moment values of the complexes are almost the same as those for the respective free lanthanide ions, it is pronounced that the 4f electrons are not at all distributed by the ligand field and hence it is unlikely that the 4f orbitals of the lanthanide(III) ions are involved in coordination in the present complexes^{19,20}.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of paramagnetic lanthanide complexes has been the subject of recent extensive reviews, which deal particularly with the physical and theoretical aspects.

The tripositive neodymium and samarium ions have the outer configuration $4f^3 5s^2 5p^6$ and $4f^6 5s^2 5p^6$ respectively and follow the Russel-Saunders *L*, *S*, *J* coupling scheme but with a certain amount of configuration interaction. The *5s* and *5p* subshells have a radial dispersion which is greater than the *4f* electrons and hence, shield the latter from the effect of coordinated ligands to a very large extent, but not completely²¹. Thus, the electronic spectra of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) can be considered as derived from the spectra of gaseous ions by a fairly small perturbation. This perturbation may be of two general types. The first is a general nephelauxetic effect owing to a drift of ligand or *5s*, *5p* electron density into the metal ion, slightly expanding the *4f* subshell and reducing the *4f-4f* interactions. The second is a crystal field splitting effect, which removes the degeneracy of the free ion levels, and which can be represented with fair success by a point negative charge model having the appropriate molecular symmetry^{22,23}.

The electronic spectra of lanthanide ions are composed of closely spaced sharp lines. The groups of lines are normally spread over an energy interval of several hundred cm^{-1} . These spectra arise from transitions among levels of f^n configurations. The usual $(2J+1)$ fold degeneracy terms of such configurations are reduced to some extent by the action of crystalline field. However, the energy levels of lanthanide ion in solid state are determined largely by spin-orbit interaction, which has a larger magnitude than the crystal field influence. Contrary to this, in transition elements, the contribution of the crystal field is more than that of the spin-orbit interaction. The *4f* electrons of lanthanides are more or less protected from the influence of lattice by the polarization of $5s^2$ and $5p^6$ closed shells. The crystal field splitting effect in the lanthanide ion is small, 200–300 cm^{-1} at the most. Thus, to a good approximation, the levels agree well with that for the free ion.

The electronic absorption bands of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) appear due to the transitions from the ground

level $^4I_{9/2}$ and $^6H_{5/2}$ to the excited *J* levels of *4f* configuration²⁴. For neodymium(III) complexes, bands observed in the regions 12000–12500, 12800, 13000–13200, 13600–14000, 17400, 18500–19100, 19500 and 20500 cm^{-1} correspond to the transitions from $^4I_{9/2}$ level to $^4F_{5/2}$, $^2H_{9/2}$, $^4F_{7/2}$, $^2S_{3/2}$, $^4F_{9/2}$, $^2G_{7/2}$, $^4G_{7/2}$ and $^4G_{9/2}$ excited energy. Samarium(III) complexes show bands in the region 17200–17500, 18500–18800, 20000, 20500–20700, 21200–21500, 23600–23900 and 25000 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transition from energy level $^6H_{5/2}$ to $^4G_{5/2}$, $^4F_{3/2}$, $^4G_{7/2}$, $^4I_{9/2}$, $^4I_{13/2}$, $^4P_{5/2}$ and $^4F_{9/2}$, respectively. It has been observed that on complexation the electronic spectral bands of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) shift to the lower energy region (nephelauxetic effect).

The nephelauxetic effect^{25,26} is quantitatively described by a nephelauxetic parameter ($\bar{\beta}$) equal to the ratio of the interelectron repulsion parameter (either Slater's integrals F_k , or Racah's parameter E_k) in the complex and in the free ion :

$$\beta = \frac{(F_k)_{\text{complex}}}{(F_k)_{\text{free ion}}} \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{\beta} = \frac{(E^k)_{\text{complex}}}{(E^k)_{\text{free ion}}}$$

As the nephelauxetic effect value $(1 - \bar{\beta})$ is small in the lanthanide complex, it can be, to a fairly good approximation defined from the ratio of the wave numbers of *f-f* transitions in the spectra of the complex and the free ion.

$$\beta \approx \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{free ion}}}$$

Since, in general case, the energy levels in the lanthanide free ions are unknown the relative nephelauxetic effects $\bar{\beta}$ and are usually determined from the experimental data using the spectra of the lanthanide aqua ions as standards.

$$\bar{\beta} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^n \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{aquo}}}$$

From the mean $\bar{\beta}$ values, Sinha's covalency parameter (δ) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) are calculated using the following formulas :

$$\delta = \frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{\bar{\beta}} \times 100 \quad \text{and} \quad b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{2} \right]^{1/2}$$

These parameters measure the amount of 4*f*-ligand mixing, i.e. covalency.

The values the parameters ($\bar{\beta}$), δ and $b^{1/2}$ of these complexes in the Table 2. The values of $\bar{\beta}$ which are less than unity and the positive values of δ and $b^{1/2}$ support partial covalent nature of bonding between the metal and ligands.

Table 2. Electronic parameters of neodymium(III) and samarium(III) complexes

Complex	$\bar{\beta}$	δ	$b^{1/2}$
C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	0.9898	1.0305	0.0714
C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	0.9800	2.0408	0.1000
C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	0.9894	1.0714	0.0728
C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	0.9793	2.1138	0.1017
C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	0.9880	1.2146	0.0775
C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	0.9774	2.3123	0.1063

Infrared spectra :

The selected infrared spectra of the Schiff bases and their metal complexes are reported in Table 3. The spectra of the free Schiff bases show band at ~ 3270 – 3150 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$, which persists almost at the same position in the complexes indicating the non-involvement of this group in bond formation²⁷. The broad band at 3350 – 3290 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 1630 – 1625 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Schiff bases may be assigned to H-bonded -OH stretching and $\nu(\text{C=N})$ vibrations. The complexes show the absence of band at 3350 – 3290 cm^{-1} due to

deprotonation of O-H group. However, the second band (1630 – 1610 cm^{-1}), is lowered by ~ 10 – 20 cm^{-1} , in the complexes indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to metal. In the far-infrared spectral region, the bands appearing at 553 – 525 , 430 – 409 and 384 – 375 cm^{-1} are usually assigned to $\nu(\text{Ln-O})$, $\nu(\text{Ln-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Ln-Cl})$ vibrations.

The bands observed around 1590 – 1545 and 1600 – 1550 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Schiff bases and their corresponding complexes may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ ring and $\nu(\text{C=C})$ (phenyl) vibrations. The complexes show broad band at 3500 – 3400 cm^{-1} , which may be due to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ of water molecules^{27,28}.

Thus the infrared spectra reveal that Schiff base ligand behave as dibasic, tetradentate ligand coordinating through two azomethine nitrogens and two phenolic oxygens through deprotonation.

¹H NMR :

The different proton magnetic resonance signals are given in Table 4. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand in DMSO-*d*₆ shows the expected two resonance due to NH protons at δ 9.8 (3 indole) and δ 4.5 ppm (hydrazide). The presence of these protons in the spectra of the complexes clearly shows that these nitrogen atoms are not engaged in complex formation. The chemical shift due to phenyl ring protons appear as multiplet at δ 6.97–8.10 ppm in the ligands and in the complexes. The spectra of the ligand exhibit singlet at δ 10.5 ppm due to phenolic

Table 3. The important infrared frequencies (in cm^{-1}) of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes

Sl. No.	Compound	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{C=N})$	$\nu(\text{Ln-N})$	$\nu(\text{Ln-O})$	$\nu(\text{Ln-Cl})$
1.	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	3435	1615	425	553	376
2.	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	3430	1612	430	545	378
3.	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	3426	1608	421	530	375
4.	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	3420	1610	418	532	384
5.	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	3435	1605	412	527	381
6.	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ ClSm	3418	1600	409	525	382

Table 4. ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts (δ in ppm) of neodymium(III) complexes at 25 °C

Sl. No.	Complex	¹ H			¹³ C		
		Aromatic ring	CH ₃	H ₂ O	Aromatic ring	CH ₃	Azomethine carbon
1.	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	7.02–7.66(m)	–	5.72(s)	110.9–156.2	–	164.3
2.	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	6.97–7.60(m)	2.68	5.70(s)	110.9–165.8	13.5	162.5
3.	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄ CINd	7.11–8.10(m)	–	5.75(s)	110.9–180.5	–	164.5

OH. The signal at δ 10.5 ppm disappears in all complexes indicating deprotonation of the enolic group. The triplet around δ 3.4 and 3.6 ppm are due to methylene protons, respectively. All complexes show a signal at δ 5.7 ppm due to protons of coordinated water molecules. The spectra of Schiff bases exhibit signals at δ 8.10–8.30 ppm due to azomethine protons. These signal shift downfield in the complexes (deshielding effect) indicating the co-ordination of azomethine nitrogen to central metal ion (compound **1** and **3**). The signal around δ 2.68 due to methyl protons (compound **2**).

¹³C NMR :

In the ¹³C NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆ (Table 4), the signal observed in the region δ 110.9–180.5 ppm as a multiplet could be assigned to aromatic carbons of ligands and complexes. In the spectra of ligand, the signal at δ 160–163 ppm may be assigned to C–O of phenolic group but these signal are at significantly downfield in the spectra of complexes. This shifting was due to the decrease of the electron density in the phenolate anions upon been coordinated to the lanthanide atom moiety during complexation. In all Schiff bases and their corresponding complexes, the peak observed at δ 154 and δ 156 ppm assignable for triazole ring carbons. All Schiff bases and complexes show triplet at δ 31 and δ 29 ppm may be assigned to methylene carbons respectively. The spectra of Schiff bases exhibit signals at δ 158 ppm due to azomethine carbons. These signal shift downfield in the complexes (deshielding effect) indicating the co-ordination of azomethine nitrogen to central metal ion. The chemical shift at δ 13.5 due to methyl carbon (compound **2**).

Thermal analysis :

The thermal behaviour of lanthanide(III) complexes under non-isothermal conditions was investigated by TG-DTG techniques in air. The complexes decomposed via intermediates to give the respective metal oxide. The organic ligands in the complexes undergo two thermal decomposition stages. The decomposition products were identified on the basis of analysis and IR spectral studies^{29–31}.

The initial stage of decomposition corresponds to the loss of two coordinated water molecules in the temperature range of 160–185 °C, accompanied by an endothermic effect; and the second stage refers to the decomposi-

tion of the anhydrous complexes to the oxides and is accompanied by a strong exothermic effect with two peaks in the temperature range of 340–600 °C. The final products of the decomposition of lanthanide complexes are suitable oxides : Nd₂O₃, Sm₂O₃. The oxides are stable at the temperature of 700 °C.

X-Ray powder diffraction pattern :

X-Ray powder diffraction pattern is a rapid analytical technique. This technique is based on constructive interference of monochromatic X-rays and a crystalline sample. These X-rays are generated by a cathode ray tube, filtered to produce monochromatic radiation to concentrate and directed toward sample^{30,31}.

X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of one representative complex (C₂₆H₂₅N₇O₄ClNd) is shown in Fig. 1. The peak broadening at lower angle is significant for the calculation of particle size, therefore size of the particles has been calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula which is given by $D = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$; where D is the size of the particle, λ is the wavelength of X-ray, β (expressed in radian) is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) after correcting the instrument peak broadening and θ is the Bragg's angle. The size of the particles is found in the range 8–25 nm which falls in the nano range.

Microbial assay :

All the newly synthesized Schiff bases and their metal complexes were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities. All the tested chemical compounds possessed variable antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* (Table 5).

The antibacterial and antifungal studies suggested that all the Schiff bases were found to be biologically active and their metal(III) complexes showed significantly enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activities. It is, however, known^{32,33} that chelation tends to make the Schiff bases act as more powerful and potent bacteriostatic agents, thus inhibiting the growth of bacteria and fungi more than the parent Schiff bases. It is suspected that factors such as solubility, conductivity, dipole moment and cell permeability mechanism (influenced by the presence of metal ions) may be the possible reasons for the increase in activity. In the case of bacteriological studies it was

Table 5. Antibacterial and antifungal results of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes (1-6) and standard

Compd.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition in %)			Antifungal activity (zone of inhibition in %)	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
1	100	45	65	75	70	75
	50	32	55	58	58	61
	25	22	41	46	45	54
2	100	42	60	71	71	73
	50	30	51	62	55	59
	25	20	40	47	42	48
3	100	–	55	65	60	65
	50	–	43	52	45	51
	25	–	35	40	34	39
4	100	–	56	62	58	66
	50	–	45	50	45	50
	25	–	33	35	31	37
5	100	50	70	80	79	83
	50	39	60	65	67	70
	25	28	49	51	56	58
6	100	48	72	75	79	80
	50	32	52	60	65	68
	25	21	40	48	57	57
Standard	100	100	100	100	100	100
	50	100	100	100	100	100
	25	100	100	100	100	100

Fig. 1

observed that some of the Schiff bases were found potentially active against all bacterial strains. Metal(III) complexes (**1-6**) of these Schiff bases were also screened against the same bacterial strains. It was evident that overall potency of the uncoordinated compounds was enhanced on coordination with metal ions, especially with *B. subtilis*. Among these metal complexes, all compounds show high activity against *B. subtilis*.

In the case of antifungal activity, the results were compared with the standard drug (fluconazole). All Schiff bases showed activity against fungal species. However, the Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes of these Schiff bases showed much enhanced activity as compared to the uncoordinated compounds. All Schiff bases show high activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*.

The biological activity of the ligands exhibited a marked enhancement on coordination with the metal ions against all fungal strains. However, the metal complexes showed good antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. It was evident from the data that this activity significantly increased on coordination. This enhancement in the activity may be rationalized on the basis that their structures mainly possess an additional C=N bond. It has been suggested that the ligands with nitrogen and oxygen donor systems inhibit enzyme activity, since the enzymes which require these groups for their activity appear to be especially more susceptible to deactivation by metal ions on coordination. Moreover, coordination reduces the polarity³⁴ of the metal ion mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups³² within the chelate ring system formed during coordination. This process, in turn, increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which favors its permeation more efficiently through the lipid layer of the microorganism³³, thus destroying them more aggressively.

Conclusion

The synthesized Schiff base ligand behave as dibasic, tetradentate ligand. The metals are coordinated to two azomethine nitrogens and two phenolic oxygens. The analytical, magnetic, IR, NMR, X-ray and thermal studies confirm the bonding of Schiff bases to metal ions. The antimicrobial studies suggested that the Schiff bases were found to be biologically active and their metal complexes showed significantly enhanced antibacterial and

antifungal activities against microbial strains in comparison to the free ligands.

All these observation put together lead us to propose the following structure (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

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References

1. V. Padmavathi, P. Thriveni, G. Sudhakar Reddy and D. Deepti, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 917.
2. M. R. Davis, E. K. Singh, H. Wahyudi, L. D. Alexander, J. B. Kunicki, L. A. Nazarova, K. A. Fairweather, A. M. Giltrap, K. A. Jolliffe and S. R. McAlpine, *Tetrahedron*, 2012, **68**, 1029.
3. M. Amir, H. Kumar and S. A. Javed, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 2056.
4. K. Sztanke, T. Tuzimski, J. Rzymowska, K. Pasternak and M. Kandefer-Szerszen, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 404.
5. C. Kus, G. A. Kılıçgil, S. Özbey, F. B. Kaynak, M. Kaya, T. Çoban and B. C. Eke, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **16**, 4294.

6. A. M. Isloor, B. Kalluraya and P. Shetty, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 3784.
7. J. Patole, D. Shingnapurkar, S. Padhye and C. Ratledge, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **16**, 1514.
8. P. Valentina, K. Ilango, M. Deepthi, P. Harusha, G. Pavani, K. L. Sindhura and C. H. Guru Keerthanana, *J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2009, **1**, 74.
9. B. S. Holla, B. Veerendra, M. K. Shivananda and B. Poojary, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **38**, 759.
10. S. V. Bhandari, K. G. Bothara, M. K. Raut, A. A. Patil, A. P. Sarkate and V. J. Mokale, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **16**, 1822.
11. K. V. Sujith, J. N. Rao, P. Shtty and B. Kalluraya, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 3697.
12. Hp Michael and C. Dines, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2004, **705**, 177.
13. D. Heng-Shan, Q. Bin, W. Kun, W. Qing-Lian and Z. Zi-Yi, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 2000, **38**, 210.
14. S. S. Papakonstantinou-Garoufalia, E. Tani, O. Todoulou, A. Papadaki-Valiraki, E. Filippators, E. D. Clercq and P. N. Kourounakis, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1988, **50**, 117.
15. R. M. Abdel-Rahman, K. O. Al-Footy and F. M. Aqlan, *Int. J. Chem. Tech. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 423.
16. H. K. Fun, C. K. Quah, A. M. Vijesh, S. Malladi and A. M. Isloor, *Acta Cryst.*, 2010, **E66**, 29.
17. A. Barry, "Procedures and theoretical considerations for testing antimicrobial agents in agar media", in : Lorian (Ed.), 'Antibiotics in Laboratory Medicine', 5th ed., Williams and Wilkins, Baltimore, 1991 (MD, 1).
18. D. J. MacLowry, M. J. Jaqua and S. T. Selpak, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1970, **20**, 46.
19. G. Rajulal and P. Indrasenan, *J. Rare Earth*, 2008, **26**, 315.
20. Yip-Foo Win, Mei-Hsuan Heng, Emad Yousif and Nasser Shalan, *International J. Phy. Sci.*, 2012, **7**, 43.
21. Bimola Huidrom, N. Ranjana Devi, Th. David Singh and N. Rajmuhon Singh, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2012, **85**, 127.
22. C. K. Jorgensen, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **4**, 73.
23. J. P. Mehta, P. N. Bhatt and S. N. Mishra, *J. Rare Earths*, 2006, **24**, 648.
24. S. S. L. Surana, M. Singh and S. N. Misra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 49.
25. R. D. Peacock, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **8**, 281.
26. D. E. Henrie and G. R. Choppin, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 477.
27. G. Singh, P. A. Singh, K. Singh, D. P. Singh, R. N. Handa and S. N. Dubey, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India*, 2002, **72**, 87.
28. P. R. Shukla, V. K. Singh, A. M. Jaiswal and J. Narain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 321.
29. Juan-Fen Wang, Fan-Tao Meng, Su-Ling Xu, Xin Liu and Jian-Jun Zhang, *Thermochimica Acta*, 2011, **521**, 2.
30. Udai P. Singh and Rajeev Kumar, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2007, **837**, 214.
31. Rajeev Kumar and Udai P. Singh, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2008, **875**, 427.
32. Z. H. Chohan, C. T. Supuran and A. Scozzafava, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **19**, 79.
33. Z. H. Chohan and M. Praveen, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **15**, 617.
34. B. N. Meyer, N. R. Ferrigni, J. E. Putnam, L. B. Jacobsen, D. E. Nichols and J. L. McLaughlin, *Planta Med.*, 1982, **45**, 31.

